

Multiple Iteration of Recycling of Carbon Fiber Composites Enable by TuFF Technology

August 7, 2025

Joseph M. Deitzel, Ph.D.

University of Delaware Center for Composite Materials

UNIVERSITY OF DELAWARE

**CENTER FOR
COMPOSITE MATERIALS**

Celebrating 50 Years

UD-CCM At a Glance-50 Years

- Founded in 1974, CCM is an internationally recognized interdisciplinary center of excellence for composites education and research
 - Started in Mechanical Engineering
 - College-wide interdisciplinary center in 1978 timeframe (ME, CHE, MSE program)
- Three-Part Mission
 - Conduct basic and applied research
 - Educate scientists and engineers
 - Transition technology to industry
- More than 3000 alumni working in Industry, Government Labs or Academia

Circular Economy of Composites Enable By the TuFF Process

DOE/EERE/ Advanced Manufacturing Office (AMO) DE-EE000303

Goal: Demonstrate for commercial Carbon/Epoxy and Carbon-Elium composites can undergo *multiple* recycling iterations and maintain near full property translation.

- *Separate the CFC polymer and fiber content with catalyst and fiber recovery (NREL lead)*
- *Demonstrate a new class of recyclable by-design polymers (CSU lead)*
- *Process the recycled carbon fiber content into high-performance CFCs (UD-CCM lead)*
- *Transition partners*
 - *Axiom Materials: Pre-Preg manufacture*
 - *Composites Automation: Composite fabrication*
 - *Arkema: Resin production*
- *Monthly technical meetings are held with DoE and Partners to share information and address challenges*

Composite Recycling Motivation:

Energy Savings, Supply Chain Stability, Environmental Stewardship

Data source: Suzuki, T; Takahashi, J;; The Ninth Japan International SAMPE Symposium; 2005

Zhang et al Composites Part B: Engineering
Volume 250, 1 February 2023, 110463

K.L. Simmons; *Sustainable Composites for Hydrogen Delivery and Storage*, SAMPE 2024

Data from <https://www.igtpan.com/Ingles/mercado-carbono.asp>

- CFC recycling approach can allow multiple iterations with fiber recovery, 50% energy saving after first recycling and ~70% after 3 recycling steps
- Majority of Industry predictions indicate Carbon fiber demand to exceed current world capacity
 - Growth in demand (10-13%) expected to exceed supply in the next decade (Drivers Wind, Pressure Vessels, etc)
 - **Recycled/Waste CF sources can potentially expand domestic sources of carbon fibers for non-aerospace applications**

Challenges of Recycled CFC

- Recycling processes such as *pyrolysis*, *thermolysis* or *solvolysis* exist and have shown to recover *rCF* without significant fiber degradation
- Typically, size reduction (conversion to short fiber) is an inherent process step during fiber recovery
- Current state-of-the-art *rCF* are used as filler in injection molding and other low-performance processes
 - Low fiber volume fraction parts
 - Aspect ratio low → reducing properties
 - Inherent *value* of CF lost
 - Down-cycled parts vs. true recycling
- Potential solutions
 - Maintaining original format: Recycling of fabric and tow
 - Aligned Discontinuous Fiber (HiPerDif, TuFF)

2017-Tailorable Universal Feedstock and Forming (TuFF)

TuFF is a feedstock comprised of a highly-aligned short fiber microstructure in tape, sheet and blank formats

- Millimeter long short fiber with filament level alignment control: $> 95\% (\pm 5^\circ)$
- High fiber volume fraction $>57\%$
- Properties equivalent to continuous fiber composites $>370\text{ksi}$ (2.55GPa) strength and $>23\text{msi}$ (159GPa) stiffness
- In-plane stretch allows metal-like forming at high throughputs
- Thin ply formats for improved damage tolerance and minimum gage designs (30gsm to standard areal weight)
- Enables recycling of carbon fiber composites

Two US Patents (10,669,659 B2 & 11,047,078) "ALIGNED DISCONTINUOUS FIBER PREFORMS, COMPOSITES AND SYSTEMS AND PROCESSES OF MANUFACTURE"

* Compression Strength and SBS are resin dominated (PEI vs 8552 Epoxy)
 **QI comparison is thin-ply (60 gsm FAW) to thick-ply (192 gsm FAW)
 OHT Strength is from TuFF1, Rest are TuFF2; Normalized values

TuFF Enables Closed-Loop Recycling of Carbon Fiber Composites

- Waste/Recycled fibers reduce material cost and environmental burden
 - Waste fiber price¹ ~\$5/lb for intermediate modulus CF
 - Recycled fiber cost² estimated at ~\$1.5/lb
- Commercial recycling processes exist and create discontinuous fiber material

- ➔ **TuFF process is key to convert recycled/waste fibers into high-performance parts**
- ➔ **Key challenges include fiber strength retention, fiber-resin adhesion, fiber length distribution, dispersion and alignment quality**

Recycled TuFF Process

VARTM/High Pressure Bladder Mold

Panel QC(C-scan, Microstructure)

Composite production

Composite testing

Mechanical Properties

Compaction testing, Alignment Quality

Preform (re-) production

Recycling

Pyrolysis
Thermolysis
Solvolysis

(Re-) Alignment of T700S Fibers within TuFF-Process

Fiber Surface preparation, Dispersion Evaluation

Challenges for Incoming Recycled Feedstock: Residue!

Waste Fiber T800
Dry fiber(minor residue)

Recycled T700/Elium
Thermolysis(~2% residue)

Recycled T800 Epoxy Prepreg
Solvolysis(5-10% Residue)

TuFF sheet made with
recycled T800

- Challenges of recycling prepreg and end-of-life parts for use in TuFF.
 - Residual material from recycling process can inhibit dispersion and resin adhesion
 - Broad distribution of fiber lengths
- Need for more efficient recycling approach and/or post recycling cleaning step
 - Elevated temperature oxidation- can harm fiber properties
 - Surfactants to aid in dispersion-requires chemicals that might adversely effect resin adhesion
 - Low temperature(50°-70°C) oxidative(ozone) cleaning-Potentially viable, but less efficient

Cleaning: Elevated Temperature Oxidation

Elium composites

Recycled T700 Fiber

Recycling leaves ~2% residue
(Low MW Oils and Char)

Recycled T700 dispersed in water

Recycled T700 SEM Micrograph

Elium/T700 FoE Recycle Iteration 1

Elium/T700 FoE Recycle Iteration 2

Adhesion Promotion for Recycle Fibers

Fiber Pullout Steps

- Measured IFSS for Recycled fibers is comparable to Virgin fiber
- Mixed Mode(resin yielding) failure is observed in all cases
- IFSS for Elium resin system is (~30 MPa) is much lower than what is typical for Epoxy-CF systems(~78 MPa))

Evaluating Failure Mode

High Pressure Bladder Molding

- Infusion parameters: 50 psi resin pressure, 200 psi bladder pressure for a total 150 psi consolidation pressure
- Polymerization: 4 hours at 25 °C, 2 hours 80 °C under pressure
- Elixir/T700 FOE Composite cross section
 - Arkema recommended Sizing
 - 1 mm thick panel with ~55% FvF

Strength, Modulus, SFTT and Fiber Length Measurements

Strength-Normalized to 45% FVF (MPa)

Modulus- Normalized to 45% FVF (GPa)

- We see 100 % retention of Stiffness across 3 recycling iterations
- Strength reduces with recycling iteration

Strength, Modulus, SFTT and Fiber Length Measurements

- Potential reasons for Strength reduction include:
 - Cumulative effect of multiple oxidative cleaning steps
 - Increase in low end of the fiber length distribution
 - Shorter fibers could lead to more end clusters

Multi-Iteration Elium/T700 Recycling Summary

100% Translation of Modulus, independent of # of recycling iterations

Third iteration of recycled fibers show ~140% improvement in strength over majority of reported recycled short fiber composites

Key factors in reduction of composite strength include:

- Loss of filament strength due to multiple oxidative cleaning steps
- Small scale clusters of fiber end groups
- Broadening of fiber length distribution
- Fiber/Resin Adhesion

1. Muhammad Furqan Khurshid , Martin Hengstermann, Chokri Cherif, Journal of Composite Materials 54(14)
2. Hecker, Marcelle D., et al. ,Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 173 (2023): 107651.

Forming Elium-infused Virgin and R3 T700 blanks via Bead Mold Setup

- Forming experiments with virgin and recycled TuFF blanks were successful
- The virgin blank had previous surface defects coming from the VARTM processing (After a pressure drop, leftover entrapped air formed a strip)
- Bead Mold Process conditions are as follows:
 - Heat press up to 155 °C
 - Prepare the blank in the mold, bag, and vacuum
 - Close the press and wait 20 minutes to get to the required resin viscosity
 - Increase pressure up to 280 psi and dwell 5 minutes
 - Start the cool-down process, remove the part

Commercial Prepregging of TuFF

(Axiom, Composite Automation and UD-CCM)

Axiom Commercial Prepreg line

CA-TuFF material being run

Final TuFF/Epoxy prepreg

- 120 gsm T700-50C TuFF dry preform with 2 64 gsm Axiom 2201 UD resin films
 - One film layer is used the carrier(100 ft roll fabricated at CA and transported to Axiom for prepreg processing)
 - No significant modification to the prepreg line was necessary

Summary & Opportunities for *rCF*

- Aligned discontinuous fiber formats have potential to re-capture original carbon fiber performance for *rCF*
 - *TuFF* formats have demonstrated 100% modulus and 74% strength to date for *rCF* compared to Virgin *TuFF* composites
- *rCF* quality must approach virgin carbon fiber quality
 - Surface cleanliness, eliminate polymer residue
 - Recycle-by-Design Resins!
 - Minimize or eliminate fiber flocks(cm) and fiber end aggregations(Microns to MM)
 - Approaches to reduce incoming breadth of fiber distribution
 - Too small – may affect strength translation
 - Too long – may affect formability
 - Sizing of *rCF* – may be needed
- Allows other unique part manufacturing processes enabled by the in-plane extensibility of *TuFF*

Acknowledgements: The Circular Economy Team!

DOE/EERE/ Advanced Manufacturing Office (AMO) DE-EE000303

- **UD-CCM**
 - Joseph Deitzel
 - Tekin Ozdemir
 - Munetaka Kubota
 - Udey Balaga
 - Markus Schwaiger
- **Composites Automation**
 - Mark Davis
 - Dirk Heider
 - Roger Crane
- **Axiom Materials**
 - Johnny Lincoln
 - Antonios Tontisakis
- **NREL**
 - Rebecca DiPucchio
 - William Michener
 - Ciaran Lahive
 - Kevin Sullivan
 - Katie Stevenson
 - Gregg Beckham
- **NREL cont**
 - Stephen Dempsey
 - Abhay Athaley
- **CSU**
 - Eswara Rao Chakkapu
 - Eugene Chen
- **Arkema**
 - Paul Boothe
 - Evan Martz
 - Mark Aubart